

CIRPASS-2 OPEN SOURCE TEST ENVIRONMENT

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CIRPASS-2 OPEN SOURCE TEST ENVIRONMENT

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Authors	Marco Volpini
Abstract	<p>This document describes the CIRPASS-2 test environment: a set of open-source, configurable software tools developed to explore data interoperability challenges for the Digital Product Passport (DPP) ecosystem. Its two central components, a Mock EU Registry and an EU Web Portal (DPP Renderer), prototype the infrastructure the European Commission is expected to deploy under ESPR, and are complemented by a DPP Validation Service and a DPP Data Extractor to form a complete integrated toolchain.</p> <p>The environment is not a production system. Its purpose is to surface the practical benefits and limitations of different DPP data exchange formats (plain JSON, JSON-LD, RDF serialisations, AAS) across industrial sectors, while remaining agnostic to the data models still under definition. All components are highly configurable at build, deploy, and runtime level, allowing pilots and the broader community to test their own use cases independently. Authentication uses OpenID Connect (OIDC) as a pragmatic baseline in place of OIDC4VC. All components are released under Apache 2.0 and deployable with a single Docker Compose command.</p>
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ABBREVIATIONS

AAS	Asset Administration Shell
API	Application Programming Interface
CD	Continuous Delivery
CI	Continuous Integration
DPP	Digital Product Passport
EORI	Economic Operators Registration and Identification
ESPR	Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation
EUDI	European Union Digital Identity
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JSON for Linked Data
JWT	JSON Web Token
MIME	Multipurpose Internet Mail Extensions
N3	Notation 3 (RDF serialisation)
OIDC	OpenID Connect
OIDC4VC	OpenID Connect for Verifiable Credentials
PKCE	Proof Key for Code Exchange
QR	Quick Response (code)
RBAC	Role-Based Access Control
RDF	Resource Description Framework
REST	Representational State Transfer
RFC	Request for Comments
rEO	Responsible Economic Operator
SHACL	Shapes Constraint Language
SPA	Single-Page Application
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
UI	User Interface
UPI	Unique Product Identifier
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier

URL	Uniform Resource Locator
UUID	Universally Unique Identifier
VC	Verifiable Credential
XML	Extensible Markup Language

1 INTRODUCTION

This document describes the CIRPASS-2 test environment: a set of open-source software tools designed to explore data interoperability challenges for the Digital Product Passport (DPP) ecosystem, with particular focus on the infrastructure that the European Commission is expected to deploy, namely a centralised EU DPP Registry and an EU Web Portal for DPP visualisation.

The environment is not a production system and does not aim to anticipate or prescribe the standards currently under definition. Its purpose, instead, is to provide a concrete, runnable prototype where the benefits and limitations of different DPP data exchange formats — plain JSON, JSON-LD, Asset Administration Shell (AAS), RDF serialisations such as Turtle — can be observed, measured, and discussed with pilots across industrial sectors (textiles, electronics, construction, automotive). Rather than locking in a single format or data model, the toolchain has been designed from the ground up to be configurable and data-model-agnostic, allowing different assumptions to be tested without code changes.

2 OBJECTIVE OF THE TEST ENVIRONMENT

The primary objective of the test environment is to explore data interoperability problems that will arise when the DPP ecosystem is deployed at scale. A DPP system involves multiple actors (Responsible Economic Operators (rEOs), public authorities, end users, downstream operators) exchanging structured product data across organisational and technological boundaries. Making that exchange work reliably, regardless of the format in which a given organisation stores or publishes its DPP data, is the central interoperability challenge.

Two components are central to this exploration, mirroring the infrastructure the EU is expected to provide under the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR):

- The Mock EU Registry: a prototype of the centralised DPP metadata registry that the European Commission must establish. Economic Operators register their DPPs here, providing a pointer (the live URL) to the actual DPP data hosted in their own decentralised repositories. The mock is fully configurable (its metadata schema, update strategy, and validation integration can all be changed at runtime) so that different assumptions about the registry API can be tested without rebuilding the software.
- The Mock EU Web Portal (DPP Renderer): a prototype of the unified web portal that the EU is expected to provide for consumers and downstream operators to access and compare DPPs across products and sectors. It includes search, rendering, and comparison capabilities, and is designed to handle DPP data from plain JSON to richly semantic JSON-LD, without requiring any upfront knowledge of the specific data schema used by a given producer.

3 KEY DESIGN ASSUMPTIONS

Three assumptions underpin the architecture of the test environment. They are explicit design decisions and each reflects a concrete interoperability question that the environment is intended to help answer.

3.1 CONTENT NEGOTIATION VIA THE LIVE URL

The live URL, whether stored in the registry or encoded in a QR code printed on a physical product, is assumed to support HTTP content negotiation as defined in RFC 9110. This means that the same URL, when accessed by a browser without any specific Accept header, returns a human-readable HTML page;

and when accessed with an Accept header of application/json or application/ld+json, returns a machine-readable version of the DPP data in the requested format.

This assumption has a significant architectural implication: it means that the same data carrier, a QR code on a product label, can serve both a human consumer scanning the code with a mobile phone and an automated system performing DPP validation or data extraction, without requiring different URLs. The test environment implements this by having the DPP Renderer Backend decorate outbound requests to the live URL with all supported MIME types in the Accept header, and by routing the response to the appropriate processing pipeline based on the returned Content-Type.

Content negotiation must be expressible through standard HTTP Accept headers. POST requests and custom headers are explicitly excluded, because they cannot be encoded in a QR code URL or triggered directly from a browser address bar.

3.2 UNKNOWN DATA SCHEMA AT EXTRACTION TIME

The development of the services described in the document assumed that the data schema of DPP documents retrieved via the live URL is not known in advance. This assumption was done for two main reasons.

The first is the state of upstream standardisation. At the time of development, the data model for the EU Registry metadata, the structure of DPP payloads, and the vocabularies to be used across industrial sectors are subjects of ongoing work. Hardcoding any specific data model into the toolchain would create a tight coupling to a moving target. By keeping the tools agnostic, the impact of upstream changes is confined to configuration updates.

The second reason is pilot parallelisation. The CIRPASS-2 project involves pilots from multiple industrial sectors, textiles, electronics, construction, automotive, each with different DPP data structures and timelines. Requiring all pilots to adopt a single agreed data model before they can integrate with the toolchain would serialise the work. Data model agnosticism inverts this dependency: each pilot can start integrating with its own existing data structures, and the toolchain adapts to them rather than the other way around.

This assumption drives the configurability of the DPP Data Extractor, which is the component responsible for pulling DPP data from the decentralised repository and indexing searchable fields into a local cache. Because no field names, property paths, or data types can be hardcoded, the extractor operates according to an externally provided configuration document that describes, for each field to be extracted, the extraction strategy to apply depending on the format of the incoming DPP. Three strategies are supported: exact property path traversal for documents compliant with the CIRPASS-2 reference ontology; type-anchored heuristic matching for JSON-LD documents with unknown vocabularies; and context-conditioned name-variant matching for plain JSON documents. All three strategies can be updated at runtime via API without restarting the application, which is the practical mechanism for adapting the environment to different pilot data structures during integration phases.

The same principle extends to the Mock EU Registry, whose metadata schema is governed by a JSON Schema document that can be replaced at runtime, and to the DPP Validator, which ships with no pre-loaded schemas and requires deployers to upload the validation resources appropriate for their DPP format. The search form in the Web Portal is not statically defined either: it is built dynamically from the list of fields returned by the DPP Data Extractor's capabilities endpoint, so that it updates automatically whenever the extraction configuration changes.

3.3 AUTHENTICATION: OIDC AS A PRAGMATIC BASELINE

Authentication in the test environment is implemented using OpenID Connect (OIDC) over OAuth 2.0, with Keycloak as the Identity Provider. This is a deliberate simplification relative to what a production DPP deployment under ESPR is expected to use: the reference architecture and the EUDI Wallet framework point toward Verifiable Credentials and OIDC4VC (OpenID Connect for Verifiable Credentials) as the long-term authentication model, where identities are issued by EU-authorized parties and presented as cryptographically verifiable tokens without central identity provider mediation.

The choice of OIDC rather than OIDC4VC was made to avoid adding authentication infrastructure complexity to a prototype environment whose primary purpose is to explore data interoperability, not authentication. OIDC is a mature, well-supported standard with production-ready libraries for both the Quarkus backend services and the Angular frontend. It is universally understood by the technical teams of pilots and consortium partners. Introducing OIDC4VC at this stage would have required building on specifications that were still in active development at the time of implementation.

All five application services share also a consistent authorization model. It uses Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) with three internal roles, admin, eu, eo (Economic Operator) mapped from external Identity Provider roles via configurable role mappings.

Onboarding a rEO to the environment requires creating a new Keycloak confidential client with service account enabled, assigning the eo role, and adding the reold and reoName attribute and corresponding protocol mapper. The client credentials (client ID and secret) are then provided to the rEO system for use in the Client Credentials flow.

4 ARCHITECTURE OVERVIEW

The test environment consists of five application services, one Identity Provider, and two shared database instances, all packaged as Docker containers and orchestrated by a single Docker Compose configuration. The entire stack is started with a single command and requires no manual configuration of databases, identity provider realms, or service-to-service wiring.

The five application services are: the Mock EU Registry, the DPP Validator, the DPP Data Extractor, the DPP Renderer Backend, and the DPP Renderer Frontend (EU Web Portal). All four backend services are implemented in Java using the Quarkus framework and expose REST APIs documented via OpenAPI. The frontend is an Angular 17 single-page application served by Nginx. All components are released as open-source software under the Apache 2.0 license and are available on the CIRPASS-2 GitHub organisation.

The below diagram shows how the various services interact.

Figure 1: Cirpass 2 test environment diagram

The environment supports two main interaction flows, which together exercise the full interoperability surface of the DPP ecosystem.

4.1 DPP REGISTRATION FLOW (REO SIDE)

A Responsible Economic Operator system authenticates to Keycloak using the OAuth 2.0 Client Credentials flow, obtaining a JWT access token. The token carries a custom `reoid` claim injected by a Keycloak protocol mapper, which encodes the operator's official identifier (e.g. a Legal Entity Identifier or EORI number) in a way that cannot be self-declared by the submitting party.

The rEO system then submits a DPP metadata registration request to the Mock EU Registry. The request body is a JSON document conforming to the active metadata schema, which includes at minimum a Unique Product Identifier (UPI), the rEO identifier, and a live URL pointing to the DPP data in the rEO's own decentralised repository. The Mock EU Registry validates the request payload against the active JSON Schema. It also fetches the DPP document from the live URL to compute the DPP data hash and retrieve the content type of the DPP data. If validation is enabled it also forwards the DPP data to the DPP Validator. On successful validation and persistence, the registry returns a registry identifier to the rEO. A proof of registration can later be obtained back by a rEO through a dedicated endpoint.

4.2 SEARCH KEY EXTRACTION (BACKGROUND PROCESS)

The DPP Data Extractor runs as a scheduled background job. At configurable intervals it queries the Mock EU Registry for the latest model-level DPP entries added or modified since the last run. For each entry it retrieves the live URL and issues an HTTP GET request with all supported Accept headers. The response is classified by format (plain JSON, JSON-LD with the CIRPASS-2 reference ontology, JSON-LD with an unknown ontology) and the appropriate extraction strategy is applied. The extracted field values are stored in a search cache database, keyed by UPI and live URL. This cache is what the EU Web Portal queries when a user performs a DPP search.

Failed extractions (due to unreachable DPP endpoints or format errors) are tracked with a retrial counter. After a configurable maximum number of retrials the entry is marked as permanently failed and excluded from future polling.

4.3 DPP VISUALISATION FLOW (CONSUMER SIDE)

An end user accesses the EU Web Portal and authenticates via the OIDC Authorization Code flow with PKCE. Once authenticated, the user can search for DPPs using the dynamically generated search form (whose fields are driven by the DPP Data Extractor's capabilities endpoint) or navigate directly to a DPP by providing its live URL, or by scanning a QR code with the integrated QR scanner component.

When rendering is requested, the DPP Renderer Backend fetches the DPP document from the live URL, negotiating the format via Accept headers. The response is processed according to its content type: plain JSON is returned as-is to the frontend; JSON-LD is expanded using the JSON-LD expansion algorithm to normalise property URLs to their fully qualified forms; other RDF serialisations (Turtle, RDF/XML, N-Triples, N3) are first converted to JSON-LD by Apache Jena and then expanded. The frontend selects a rendering strategy based on the processed content: an abstract collapsible-panel strategy for plain JSON and unknown-ontology JSON-LD, and a dedicated ontology-aware strategy for JSON-LD compliant with the CIRPASS-2 reference ontology, which maps specific entity types to purpose-built Angular components.

The comparison capability allows a user to select multiple DPPs and compare specific properties side by side in a tabular view. Property paths are specified using a structured syntax that supports type-filtered graph traversal (e.g. `hasProperty[*@type=CarbonFootprint].numericalValue`) and are translated internally to SPARQL queries executed over each DPP. Multiple path definitions per field, each bound to a different vocabulary namespace, allow practical comparison across DPPs using different but structurally similar ontologies, without requiring a full semantic reasoner.

5 SERVICE CATALOGUE

The following table summarises the services included in the test environment and their roles in the interoperability exploration.

TABLE 1 : CAPTION FOR THE AGENDA TABLE

Service Name	Service Description
Keycloak	Identity and Access Management. Pre-configured with the cirpass-2 realm, including all OIDC clients for both machine-to-machine (Client Credentials) and browser-based (Authorization Code + PKCE) flows.
Mock EU Registry	Prototype of the EU DPP centralised registry. Accepts DPP metadata registration from rEOs, stores a live URL pointing to the actual DPP in the decentralised repository, and exposes a search API. Metadata schema is fully configurable at runtime via JSON Schema.
DPP Validator	Validates DPP payloads against JSON Schema (for plain JSON) or SHACL templates (for JSON-LD and RDF). Automatically selects the matching schema or template based on Jaccard similarity and semantic metadata. Invoked by the Mock EU Registry when DPP validation is enabled.
DPP Data Extractor	Background job that polls the Mock EU Registry, fetches DPP documents from the decentralised repository via their live URLs, and extracts searchable field values into a local cache. Extraction configuration is data-model-agnostic and updatable at runtime. Exposes a capabilities endpoint consumed by the Web Portal to build its dynamic search form.
DPP Renderer BE	Backend for the EU Web Portal. Exposes REST APIs for DPP fetch (with format normalisation to JSON or expanded JSON-LD), search over the extraction cache, and cross-DPP property comparison via SPARQL-backed path extraction.
DPP Renderer FE (EU Web Portal)	Angular 17 single-page application. Provides DPP search, rendering (abstract and ontology-aware strategies), comparison, and QR code scanning. Runtime-configurable via env.js without image rebuilds.